

DESIGN OF LARGE SPACE ANTENNA COMPOSITE RIM

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KEYWORDS: large antenna, thin-walled rim, motion equations, vibration frequency, finite difference method

INTRODUCTION

The large antennas are an integral part of modern space vehicles. Space antennas should have sizable diameter, and at the same time, their design should satisfy high rigidity requirements. At present there are various approaches to form the sizable diameter antennas on the orbit. One of such approaches is to form the antenna rim as a ring with thin-walled circular cross section (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Antenna (a), antenna rim (b) and antenna cross section (c)

Such rim is made of a composite material, its curing stage not being carried out in the ground manufacturing. The folded antenna in the hermetical container is delivered by a space vehicle to the orbit. Then rim internal area is filled with compressed air and the soft rim shell is opened and stretched. Under environment influence the composite rim is formed into the rigid structure due to final curing. The equations describing motion of a composite ring, modeling the large space antenna rim are received in the present paper. The analysis of influence on the vibration frequency of the antenna rim of various design parameters is executed. The design algorithms of the antenna rim are offered.

MODEL AND DESIGN PROBLEM

Mathematical model of the rim is the thin-walled ring fixed in one point (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. The antenna rim model

This fixing simulates fastening of the rim to a space vehicle or to its extending bar. The external diameter of the rim is predefined; therefore the rim design is reduced to definition of the cross-section radius r and reinforcing angle ϕ to provide maximal rigidity. Traditionally, for space structures the rim rigidity is estimated by the first vibration frequency. The ring cross section has two axes of symmetry and, therefore, the ring motion can be described by two groups of the equations. First of them describes the ring motion in its plane, and second group describes the ring motion out of its plane. The rim vibrations are described by the set of the equations, which takes into account transverse shear strain of cross section, an extensibility of ring axis and the rotation inertia. The stiffness parameters in these equations depend on the cross section radius, elastic parameters of a composite material and a reinforcing angle.

The set of the equations, describing the ring vibration in its plane includes motion equations

$$\frac{\partial N}{R \partial \beta} + \frac{Q_t}{R} - B_p \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad \frac{\partial Q_t}{R \partial \beta} - \frac{N}{R} - B_p \frac{\partial^2 w_t}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad \frac{\partial M_t}{R \partial \beta} - Q_t - D_{tp} \frac{\partial^2 \theta_t}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

constitutive relations

$$N = B \varepsilon \quad M_t = D_t \chi_t \quad Q_t = K_t \psi_t \quad (2)$$

and geometric relations

$$\varepsilon = \frac{\partial u}{R \partial \beta} + \frac{w_t}{R} \quad \chi_t = \frac{\partial \theta_t}{R \partial \beta} \quad \psi_t = \theta_t - \frac{u}{R} + \frac{\partial w_t}{R \partial \beta} \quad (3)$$

In Eqs. (1), (2), (3) β is the angle coordinate measured from the fixed point, t is the time, N , Q_t are the axial and transverse forces, M_t is the bending moment (Fig. 3), u , w_t are the displacements, θ_t is the rotation angle (Fig. 3), ε is the normal strain of the ring center line, χ_t is the curvature change of the center line of the ring in its plane, ψ_t is the transverse shear strain, B is the axial stiffness, D_t is the bending stiffness, K_t is the transverse shear stiffness, B_p is the axial inertia coefficient, D_{tp} is the rotation inertia coefficient.

Fig. 3. In-plane forces and displacements

Let us derive a set of equations including only displacements u , w_1 and rotation angle θ_1 . Substituting sequentially Eqs. (2), (3) into Eqs. (1), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} B \frac{\partial^2 u}{R^2 \partial \beta^2} - \frac{K_1}{R^2} u + \frac{B+K_1}{R} \frac{\partial w_1}{R \partial \beta} + \frac{K_1}{R} \theta_1 - B_\rho \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2} &= 0 \\ -\frac{B+K_1}{R} \frac{\partial u}{R \partial \beta} + K_1 \frac{\partial^2 w_1}{R^2 \partial \beta^2} - \frac{B}{R^2} w_1 + K_1 \frac{\partial \theta_1}{R \partial \beta} - B_\rho \frac{\partial^2 w_1}{\partial t^2} &= 0 \\ \frac{K_1}{R} u - K_1 \frac{\partial w_1}{R \partial \beta} + D_1 \frac{\partial^2 \theta_1}{R^2 \partial \beta^2} - K_1 \theta_1 - D_{1\rho} \frac{\partial^2 \theta_1}{\partial t^2} &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Let us assume the in-plane ring motion in the form of

$$u = u(\beta) \sin \omega_1 t \quad w_1 = w_1(\beta) \sin \omega_1 t \quad \theta_1 = \theta_1(\beta) \sin \omega_1 t \quad (5)$$

where ω_1 is the circular frequency of the in-plane ring vibration.

Substitution of the expressions (5) into Eqs. (4) yields the following set of the ordinary homogeneous differential equations

$$\begin{aligned} B \frac{d^2 u}{R^2 d\beta^2} - \frac{K_1}{R^2} u + \frac{B+K_1}{R} \frac{dw_1}{R d\beta} + \frac{K_1}{R} \theta_1 - B_\rho \omega_1^2 u &= 0 \\ -\frac{B+K_1}{R} \frac{du}{R d\beta} + K_1 \frac{d^2 w_1}{R^2 d\beta^2} - \frac{B}{R^2} w_1 + K_1 \frac{d\theta_1}{R d\beta} - B_\rho \omega_1^2 w_1 &= 0 \\ \frac{K_1}{R} u - K_1 \frac{dw_1}{R d\beta} + D_1 \frac{d^2 \theta_1}{R^2 d\beta^2} - K_1 \theta_1 - D_{1\rho} \omega_1^2 \theta_1 &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

The stiffness coefficients B , K_1 , D_1 for thin-walled circular cross section (Fig. 2) have the following form [1]

$$B = 2\pi B_{11} \quad D_1 = \pi^3 B_{11} \quad K_1 = \pi B_{33} \quad (7)$$

where B_{11} and B_{33} are the wall membrane stiffness. Consider the wall structure formed by composite layers arranged at angles $\pm\varphi$ (Fig. 2). For a large number of layers, we can consider the wall material as a homogeneous orthotropic material. Then the B_{11} and B_{33} stiffness are specified by

$$B_{11} = A_{11} h \quad B_{33} = A_{33} h \quad (8)$$

where h is the wall thickness and

$$\begin{aligned} A_{11} &= \bar{E}_1 \cos^4 \varphi + \bar{E}_2 \sin^4 \varphi + 2(\bar{E}_1 \nu_{12} + 2G_{12}) \sin^2 \varphi \cos^2 \varphi \\ A_{33} &= (\bar{E}_1 + \bar{E}_2 - 2\bar{E}_1 \nu_{12}) \sin^2 \varphi \cos^2 \varphi + G_{12} (\cos^2 \varphi - \sin^2 \varphi)^2 \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

in which $\bar{E}_1 = E_1 / (1 - \nu_{12} \nu_{21})$, $\bar{E}_2 = E_2 / (1 - \nu_{12} \nu_{21})$

Here E_1 , E_2 are modules of elasticity along and across the direction of reinforcement, respectively, G_{12} is the shear modulus, ν_{12} and ν_{21} are the Poisson's ratios.

The inertia coefficients B_ρ and $D_{1\rho}$ have the form

$$B_\rho = 2\pi \rho h \quad D_{1\rho} = \pi^3 \rho h \quad (10)$$

where ρ is the density of the wall material.

Let us transform the equations (6) into the dimensionless form. Substituting Eqs. (7), (8), (10) into Eqs. (6) after some manipulations, we get

$$\begin{aligned} -2 \frac{d^2 u}{d\beta^2} + \alpha u - (2 + \alpha) \frac{dw_1}{d\beta} - \alpha \tau \eta_1 - 2\lambda_1 f u &= 0 \\ (2 + \alpha) \frac{du}{d\beta} - \alpha \frac{d^2 w_1}{d\beta^2} + 2w_1 - \alpha \tau \frac{d\eta_1}{d\beta} - 2\lambda_1 f w_1 &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

$$-\alpha\tau u + \alpha\tau \frac{dw_i}{d\beta} - \frac{d^2\eta_i}{d\beta^2} + \alpha\tau^2\eta_i - \lambda_i f\eta_i = 0$$

$$\text{where } \eta_i = r\theta_i \quad \alpha = A_{33} / A_{11} \quad \tau = R / r \quad f = E_i / A_{11} \quad (12)$$

$$\lambda_i = \rho R^2 \omega_i^2 / E_i \quad (13)$$

Let us use the finite difference method for solution of the homogeneous differential equations (11). The dimensionless parameter λ_i corresponding to the first frequency of the in-plane ring vibration, is determined as the lowest eigenvalue of the set of the homogeneous linear algebraic equations. In these equations, the unknowns are the values of the u , w_i , η_i functions at the points of the finite difference mesh.

The analysis of influence of reinforcing angle φ and the ratio of radiuses τ on the frequency parameter λ_i for in-plane vibration mode was performed. The φ angle varied from 0° to 90° , and the radiuses ratio τ varied from 5 to 50. The frequency parameter λ_i as a function of the φ , τ arguments is plotted in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. The frequency parameter λ_i as a function of the φ , τ arguments

Specifying different values of τ ranging from 5 to 50, we define, for each of these values, the φ angle, which gives the maximum value $\lambda_{i\max}$. The selection of $\lambda_{i\max}$ values is given in Table 1.

Table 1. The frequency parameter $\lambda_{i\max}$

τ	φ°	$\lambda_{i\max} \cdot 10^5$
5	19	363.47
10	13	125.49
15	9	63.98
20	5	39.36
25	0	27.11
30	0	20.09
35	0	15.70
40	0	12.79
45	0	10.75
50	0	9.27

The analysis of the obtained results makes it possible to conclude, that as the ratio of radiuses τ increases, the φ angle tends to zero. The formula $\lambda_{i\max} = \rho R^2 \omega_i^2 / E_i$ and the table

data allow to define the cross-section radius r and the φ angle providing the required frequency ω_l .

The set of the equations, describing the out-of-plane ring vibration includes motion equations

$$\frac{\partial Q_2}{R \partial \beta} - B_\rho \frac{\partial^2 w_2}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad \frac{\partial M_2}{R \partial \beta} - \frac{M}{R} - Q_2 - D_{2\rho} \frac{\partial^2 \theta_2}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad \frac{\partial M}{R \partial \beta} + \frac{M_2}{R} - D_\rho \frac{\partial^2 \theta}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (14)$$

constitutive relations

$$Q_2 = K_2 \psi_2 \quad M = D \chi \quad M_2 = D_2 \chi_2 \quad (15)$$

and geometric relations

$$\psi_2 = \theta_2 + \frac{\partial w_2}{R \partial \beta} \quad \chi_2 = \frac{\partial \theta_2}{R \partial \beta} + \frac{\theta}{R} \quad \chi = \frac{\partial \theta}{R \partial \beta} + \frac{\theta_2}{R} \quad (16)$$

Here Q_2 is the transverse force, M_2 is the bending moment, M is the twisting moment (Fig. 5), w_2 is the displacement, θ and θ_2 are the rotation angles (Fig. 5), ψ_2 is the transverse shear strain, χ is the axis twisting, χ_2 is the axis curvature change, K_2 is the transverse shear stiffness of the ring cross section, D is the twisting stiffness, D_2 is the bending stiffness, D_ρ is the twisting inertia coefficient, $D_{2\rho}$ is the rotation inertia coefficient.

Fig. 5. Out-of-plane forces and displacements

Substitution of Eqs. (15), (16) into Eqs. (14) yields

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{K_2}{R^2} \frac{\partial^2 w_2}{\partial \beta^2} + \frac{K_2}{R} \frac{\partial \theta_2}{\partial \beta} - B_\rho \frac{\partial^2 w_2}{\partial t^2} &= 0 \\ -\frac{K_2}{R} \frac{\partial w_2}{\partial \beta} + \frac{D_2}{R^2} \frac{\partial^2 \theta_2}{\partial \beta^2} - (K_2 + \frac{D}{R^2}) \theta_2 - \frac{D_2 + D}{R^2} \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial \beta} - D_{2\rho} \frac{\partial^2 \theta_2}{\partial t^2} &= 0 \\ \frac{D + D_2}{R^2} \frac{\partial \theta^2}{\partial \beta} + \frac{D}{R^2} \frac{\partial^2 \theta}{\partial \beta^2} - \frac{D_2}{R^2} \theta - D_\rho \frac{\partial^2 \theta}{\partial t^2} &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

Let us assume the out-of-plane ring motion in the form of

$$w_2 = w_2(\beta) \sin \omega_2 t \quad \theta_2 = \theta_2(\beta) \sin \omega_2 t \quad \theta = \theta(\beta) \sin \omega_2 t \quad (18)$$

where ω_2 is the circular frequency of the out-of-plane ring vibration.

Substituting the displacement and the angles in Eqs. (17), we arrive at the following ordinary homogeneous differential equations

$$\frac{K_2}{R^2} \frac{d^2 w_2}{d\beta^2} + \frac{K_2}{R} \frac{d\theta_2}{d\beta} + B_\rho \omega_2^2 w_2 = 0$$

$$-\frac{K_2}{R} \frac{dw_2}{d\beta} + \frac{D_2}{R^2} \frac{d^2\theta}{d\beta^2} - (K_2 + \frac{D}{R^2})\theta_2 - \frac{D+D_2}{R^2} \frac{d\theta}{d\beta} + D_{2\rho} \omega^2 \theta_2 = 0 \quad (19)$$

$$\frac{D+D_2}{R^2} \frac{d\theta}{d\beta} + \frac{D}{R^2} \frac{d^2\theta}{d\beta^2} - \frac{D_2}{R^2} \theta + D_\rho \omega^2 \theta = 0$$

The stiffness coefficients K_2 , D_2 , D and the inertia coefficients D_ρ , $D_{2\rho}$ have the form [1]

$$K_2 = \pi r A_{33} h \quad D = 2\pi r^3 A_{33} h \quad D_2 = \pi r^3 A_{11} h \quad D_{2\rho} = \pi r^3 \rho h \quad D_\rho = 2\pi r^3 \rho h \quad (20)$$

As in the case of the in-plane ring motion, let us transform the equations (19) into the dimensionless form. Substituting Eqs. (20) into Eqs. (19), we obtain

$$-\alpha \frac{d^2 w_2}{d\beta^2} - \alpha \tau \frac{d\eta_2}{d\beta} - 2\lambda_2 f w_2 = 0$$

$$\alpha \tau \frac{dw_2}{d\beta} - \frac{d^2 \eta_2}{d\beta^2} + \alpha(2 + \tau^2) \eta_2 + (1 + 2\alpha) \frac{d\eta}{d\beta} - \lambda_2 f \eta_2 = 0 \quad (21)$$

$$-(1 + 2\alpha) \frac{d\eta_2}{d\beta} - 2\alpha \frac{d^2 \eta}{d\beta^2} + \eta - 2\lambda_2 f \eta = 0$$

$$\text{Here } \eta = r\theta \quad \eta_2 = r\theta_2 \quad \alpha = A_{33} / A_{11} \quad f = E_1 / A_{11} \quad (22)$$

$$\lambda_2 = \rho R^2 \omega^2 / E_1 \quad (23)$$

The finite difference method likewise has been used to solve the homogeneous differential equations of out-of-plane motion (21). The frequency parameter λ_2 is determined as the smallest eigenvalue of a corresponding set of the homogeneous linear algebraic equations. The influence of the φ angle and the ratio of radiuses τ on the frequency parameter λ_2 for out-of-plane vibration is illustrated in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. The influence of the φ angle and the ratio of radiuses τ on the frequency parameter λ_2 for out-of-plane vibration

Looking over different values of the ratio of radiuses τ , we seek for each of these values the φ angle, which gives the maximum value λ_{2max} . Certain λ_{2max} values are tabulated in Table 2.

Table 2. The frequency parameter λ_{2max}

τ	φ°	$\lambda_{2max} \cdot 10^5$
5	33	173.55
10	33	46.23
15	33	20.97
20	33	12.00
25	33	7.82
30	33	5.54
35	32	4.16
40	33	3.27
45	33	2.66
50	33	2.22

It follows from Table 2 that the maximum values of frequency parameter λ_{2max} are realized at $\varphi=33^\circ$. Therefore, the wall structures with the reinforcement angles greater than 33° there is no need to consider. The formula $\lambda_{2max} = \rho R^2 \omega_2^2 / E_1$ and the table data allow to obtain the cross-section radius r , providing the restriction imposed on the out-of-plane vibration frequency. As this takes place, the in-plane rim rigidity will be provided with a margin.

Let us consider the design case when the restrictions are imposed on both frequencies of the two vibration modes (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7. The in-plane (a) and out-of-plane (b) vibration modes

Let us obtain the ratio of frequencies ω_1 and ω_2 . From Eqs. (13) and (23) we have

$$\frac{\omega_1}{\omega_2} = \sqrt{\frac{\lambda_1}{\lambda_2}} \quad (24)$$

The ratio ω_1/ω_2 as a function of the ratio of radiuses τ and the reinforcing angle φ , varying from 0° up to 35° is illustrated in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8. The ω_1/ω_2 value as a function of the ratio of radiuses τ and the reinforcing angle φ

As evident from Fig. 8, the value of ω_1/ω_2 changes in the range from 1.3 to 3.6. It allows to appoint the real restrictions, imposed on both frequencies. The curves shown in Fig. 8 can be used as nomogram for the approximate definition of the ratio of radiuses τ and the reinforcing angle φ , providing the required relation of the frequencies.

More exact values of τ and φ can be determined from the solution of the following nonlinear equations

$$\lambda_1(\tau, \varphi) - \sigma_1 = 0 \quad \lambda_2(\tau, \varphi) - \sigma_2 = 0 \quad (25)$$

where $\sigma_1 = \rho R^2 \bar{\omega}_1^2 / E_1$ $\sigma_2 = \rho R^2 \bar{\omega}_2^2 / E_1$

Here $\bar{\omega}_1$ and $\bar{\omega}_2$ are the required values of the frequencies.

CONCLUSIONS

The equations describing motion of a composite ring, modeling the large space antenna rim are received in the present paper. The external diameter of the rim is predefined, therefore the rim design is reduced to definition of the cross-section diameter and reinforcing angle to provide maximal rigidity. The vibrations of the rim are described by the set of the equations, which includes the motion equations, constitutive and geometric equations. These equations take into account transverse shear strain of cross section, an extensibility of ring axis and the rotation inertia. The stiffness parameters in these equations depend on the cross section radius, elastic parameters of a composite material and a reinforcing angle. The finite difference method has been used to solve the differential equations of motion. The analysis of influence of the reinforcing angle and the ratio of radiuses on the first frequency for two vibrations modes - in the ring plane and out of the ring plane was performed. The developed model allows to define the first frequency of the ring vibrations for various combinations of design parameters. The design algorithms of antenna rim for two variants of restrictions are offered. In the first variant the restriction, imposed on the out-of-plane ring vibration frequency is taken into account. In the second variant the restrictions, imposed on both frequencies of the two vibration modes are considered.

REFERENCES

1. Vasiliev V.V., *Mechanics of Composite Structures*. Taylor & Francis, 1993.